

THE IMPORTANCE OF ASSESSMENT, AND ITS IMPACT IN LEARNING PROCESS

Yozuvchi: **Bozorova Husnnora Bahrillo qizi**

Ilmiy rahbar: **Shaxnoza Rustamova Aripovna**

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8011375>

Abstract The assessment is a significant and integral part of educational process. It is like a motivation for students during the learning classes. Namely, teachers can improve interests and activeness of students by using assessments. For example, if one learner takes an excellent mark from his English teacher, he will try to acquire knowledge much harder and be the best and smart student in his class. Moreover, it is used by teachers in gathering information about what and how their students are learning. By assessing homework, which is done by their students, the teacher is able to not only inform whether the students have mastered the previous lesson or not, but also determine the difficulties of students in learning process. In one word, an assessment is a feedback whether teaching practice is working. According to the results of assessments of students, teachers can set an objective of the class, create the effective and proper atmosphere, select appropriate methods and techniques in order to enhance the level of students in learning the subject better and faster.

Keywords: feedback, motivation, types of assessment, entry behavior, principles, Assessment has a vital role in education and it has a critical role in the teaching process. Through appropriate assessment, teachers are able to classify and grade their students, and structure their teaching accordingly, as well as students can be provided with feedback effectively. Recently, educators and scientists have been becoming more interested in the requirements of assessment procedures in the scope of foreign language teaching and the learning process, as forms of assessment have been changing.

Assessment has a vital impact in the education process to inform and improve ongoing learning, and plays a significant role (Cowie & Bell, 1999). According to Pierce, (2002; cited in Kırmızı & Kömeç, 2016), assessment is a crucial part of any learning and teaching activity. It not only informs instructional decisions made on a day-to-day basis and helps diagnose student strengths and weaknesses related to classroom instruction, but also provides specific feedback to students in support of their learning. Assessment also provides immediate feedback for teachers to shape their teaching practices according to the learning styles of their students. To assess student achievement and determine grades, teachers should use different tests. Tests, examinations and evaluation models are important tools, utilized as a measure of the learning process. Assessment, teaching and learning are inextricably linked, as each informs the others. Assessment is a powerful process that can either optimize or embarrass learning, influencing by how it's applied.

For teachers

Assessment for learning aids teachers to collect information to:

- organize and adjust teaching and learning programs for individual students, groups of students and the whole class
- identify students' strengths so that both teachers and students can build on them
- determine students' learning needs in an accurate and productive way so they can be addressed
- include parents and families in their children's learning.

For students

- Assessment for learning gives students information and guidance so they can pinpoint and manage the next steps in their learning.
- Assessment for learning uses data in order to direct from what has been learned to what needs to be learned next.

Describing assessment for learning

Assessment for learning should use a range of approaches. These may include:

- ❖ day-to-day activities (such as learning conversations)
- ❖ a simple mental note taken by the teacher during observation
- ❖ student self and peer assessments
- ❖ a detailed analysis of a student's work
- ❖ assessment tools (which may be written items, structured interview questions or items teachers make up themselves).

What matters most is not so much the form of the assessment, but how the information gathered is used to improve teaching and learning.

Types of assessment

On the basis of how it is used and how the results are interpreted, assessment is classified into different types.

1. Placement Assessment
2. Formative Assessment
3. Diagnostic Assessment
4. Summative Assessment

Placement Assessment

Before organizing the teaching-learning activities in order to take the measurements of the entry behavior or previous knowledge of learners, this type of assessment is managed. Another aim is to know whether learner is able to gain the new learning experience which is reluctant to the preceding knowledge. The key word that is employed for placement assessment is the "entry behavior". Assessment of entry behavior is done just before teaching commences. In the teaching-learning process, before teaching a new topic, a teacher should know the previous knowledge of students. This assists the teacher to select teaching-learning activities according to the learners' knowledge which is acquired previously.

Formative assessment

It is an assessment used to control students' learning progress in the duration of instruction with the purpose of providing on-going feedback to students and teachers which is regarded to success and failure of teaching and learning. For the first time in the year 1967, Michel Scriven used the concept of formative assessment in the field of curriculum evaluation. Scriven (1991) defined it as "Developmental evaluation is normally directed during the turn of events or improvement of a program or item (or individual, etc) and it is led, frequently at least a couple of times, for in house staff of the program with the degree to get to the next level". If the definition is reviewed, it is clear that the aim of conducting formative assessment is to manage the learning progress of the learners; it is also to know whether the learning objectives have been achieved or not and to provide feedback on the teaching-learning process. The key word in this assessment is "mastery of learning" or "learning progress". Formative Assessment also enables the teacher to rethink instructional strategies, activities,

and content which is based on students understanding and accomplishment. His/her role here is corresponding to that of a teacher. This assessment can be as informal as observing the learner's performance or as formal as a written test. Formative Assessment is the most powerful and essential type of assessment to improving student understanding and performance.

Diagnostic Assessment

It is the assessment which is managed along with formative assessment during the instructional process. It is carried out based on the information which is obtained from formative assessment. Diagnostic assessment is specially conducted for removing challenges of learners in learning. For example, if it is found that a learner has not comprehended certain concepts in a particular topic, then to help him/her understand these concepts, diagnostic assessment is conducted and remediation is provided. This is conducted by diagnostic remedial test. The key word in diagnostic assessment is "assessment of learning difficulties". Diagnostic assessment not only tackles learning difficulties of learners but also clarifies and provides remedies for personal and psychological problems.

Summative assessment

Summative assessment is conducted to know the Assessment: Basics terminal behavior of learner. The key word in summative assessment is "certification". Summative assessment is conducted after execution of the whole course. Feedback provided in summative assessment is terminal in nature and cannot be used for modification of learners' behavior because it is conducted at the end of a term. Students get endorsement or are elevated to the higher class in view of summative evaluation. Different techniques and tools used in summative assessment are verbal or non-verbal tests, and teacher make consistent tests. Summative assessment exhibits the quantity of a learner's success in meeting the assessment criteria used to measure the intended learning outcomes of a module or program, and which contributes to the final mark given for the module. For all these reasons the validity and reliability of summative assessment are of the greatest importance. Summative

evaluation can give data that has developmental/symptomatic worth. Anderson et al.

(246) compose that summative appraisal is typically formal and in light of explicit data sources like tests, ventures and articles. Criticism to summative assessment methods is that they do not support high quality learning. (Havnes & McDowell 4) Functions of assessment

- ❖ Monitoring the progress
- ❖ Decision making
- ❖ Screening
- ❖ Diagnostic process
- ❖ Placement of students in remedial courses
- ❖ Instructional planning
- ❖ Evaluation of instructional program
- ❖ Feedback
- ❖ Motivation
- ❖ Principles of assessment for learning
- ❖ Learning to learn

- ❖ Building students' assessment capability
- ❖ Engaging and motivating
- ❖ Content knowledge
- ❖ Planned and communicated
- ❖ Progressive and cumulative
- ❖ Supports teaching and learning goals
- ❖ Recognizes social and cultural aspects of assessment
- ❖ Teaching inquiry
- ❖ Perspectives of Assessment:
- ❖ Assessment for learning,
- ❖ Assessment of learning,
- ❖ Assessment as learning.

Assessment for learning: where assessment assists teachers to gain insight into what students understand in order to plan and guide instruction, and give useful feedback to students.

Assessment as learning: where students evolve an awareness of how they learn and utilize that awareness to adjust and advance their learning, taking an increased responsibility for their learning.

Evaluation of realizing: where evaluation illuminates understudies, educators and guardians, as well as the more extensive instructive local area, of accomplishment at one point in time to celebrate achievement, sort out mediations and keep up with proceeded with progress.

Conclusion

Assessments can provide both teachers and students with data on the level of knowledge, skills, difficulties in foreign language learning and which activities and methods are the most profitable. Testing is a means of evaluation of student activities and can be used for a clear criterion or scale. The word assessment means the consideration of a person and an evaluation of them, and has a wider rationale rather than testing (Akpinar & Çakildere, 2013; Brown, 2004), which can be used with the objects, to test, gauge and evaluate. In the light of substitute assessments, teachers may determine what is significant in their teaching process and opt assessment strategies compatible for the characteristics of the learners.

Acknowledging and organizing principles of assessment improves the planning of assessment of a second language. So, the following issues have to be taken into account by the teacher in the outlining of teaching foreign languages with regard to assessment:

1. Instruction and assessment should character one another.
2. All types of assessments are emphatic while using a foreign language.
3. Assessment must have a fundamental place in teaching.
4. Assessment principles have to be taken into consideration for making teaching materials by the teachers for the students.
5. Negative factors that influence students, such as anxiety and worry, should be the center of teacher's attention.

To sum up, the importance of assessment in the process of language teaching has been known recently. Assessment is very crucial for the students to obtain a language. It plays a vital role in the process of learning, and links students to new knowledge utilizing their current capacities.

References:

1. Akpınar, K., & Çakildere, B. (2013). Washback Effects of High-Stakes Language Tests of Turkey (KPDS and UDS) on Productive and Receptive Skills of Academic Personnel. *Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies*, 9(2), 81-9
2. Anderson, Lorin W., Krathwohl, David R., Airasian, Peter W., Cruikshank, Kathleen A., Mayer, Richard E., Pintrich, James Raths, and Wittrock, Merlin C. *A Taxonomy for Learning, Teaching, and Assessing*. New York: Addison Wesley Longman, Inc. 2001
3. Cowie, B., & Bell, B. (1999). A Model of Formative Assessment in Science Education. *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice*, 6(1), 101-116. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09695949993026>
4. Havnes, Anton, and McDowell, Liz. "Introduction: Assessment dilemmas in contemporary learning cultures." *Balancing Dilemmas in Assessment and Learning in Contemporary Education*. Ed. Havnes, Anton., and McDowell, Liz New York: Routledge, 2008. 3- 14
5. Kırmızı, Ö., & Kömeç, F. (2016). An Investigation of Performance-Based Assessment at High Schools. *Üniversitepark Bülten*, 5(1-2), 53-65. <https://doi.org/10.22521/unibulletin.2016.512.5>
6. Scriven Michael (1967). *The Methodology of Evaluation*, Quoted in N.E. Gronlund, (1981)+. *Measurement and Evaluation in Teaching*. New York: Holt, Rinehart and Winston, Inc.